

Genetic Influences on Mental Health

Nguyen Minh Trang ✉

Diplomatic Academy of Vietnam, Viet Nam

Jennifer Tran Cao Van

VSTAR SCHOOL, Viet Nam

Do Hoang Phuong Trang

Nguyen Thi Minh Khai high school, Viet Nam

Abstract

Mental and physical health are two most crucial factor that deciding the happiness and development of each individual in the world. Physical health problem is quite obvious and easy to be recognized through advanced and modern technology. However, mental health sometimes invisible and hard to be revealed by the machines and the patients themselves. It is believed that genetic factors play a significant role in the development of various mental health conditions. Based on extensive research, scientists categorize major mental illnesses into several types, including schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, depression, and anxiety disorders. The primary causes of these mental health issues are rooted in organic, psychological, abnormal physical structures, and endogenous factors. Treatment for mental health disorders includes a range of therapies such as medication, electroconvulsive therapy (ECT), transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS), psychotherapy, and rehabilitation. It is essential for individuals to adopt different measures such as regular exercise, maintaining a positive attitude towards life's challenges, helping others, and following a healthy diet to escape from mental health issues. This research used a survey conducted with over 200 participants to understand more about the relationship between mental health and genetics, offering recommendations for reducing the incidence of mental health issues.

Introduction

Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Mental health is a very broad category. For a long time, there are many incorrect concepts about pathology, mental disorders, and causes of illness, so mental health has not been properly recognized. Sometimes, people have confusion between people with normal mental health and people with abnormal mental health. Mental health refers to a state of well-being in which an individual can cope with the normal stresses of life, work productively, and contribute to their community. It encompasses emotional, psychological, and social well-being and is crucial for overall health. Mental disorders can significantly impair an individual's ability to function and affect their quality of life [1,2]. The recognition of mental health's importance has led to increased efforts in understanding and treating various mental health conditions. Mental health is a crucial component of overall well-being, influencing our thoughts, emotions

and daily functioning. The World Health Organization defines mental health as a state where individuals can cope with stress, work productively, and contribute to his or her community [1]. Research shows that mental health issues, such as depression and anxiety, impair quality of life and productivity. Additionally, untreated mental health problems can lead to chronic physical illnesses, including cardiovascular disease.

Mental health and physical health are deeply interconnected and have close interrelationship with each other. People often focus on physical well-being by promoting exercise, balanced diets, and regular medical check-ups and sometimes forget that mental health is just as crucial for overall quality of life. Good mental health forms the foundation for how we think, feel, and act. It influences our ability to manage stress, make decisions and enjoy life. Good mental health can enhance physical health by promoting a positive outlook, fostering resilience, and enabling better self-care practices.

More Information

How to cite this article: Trang NM, Van JTC, Trang DHP. Genetic Influences on Mental Health. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(5):247-55.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(5).25

Keywords:

Genetic Influences,
mental health.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Genetics plays a pivotal role in determining an individual's susceptibility to various health conditions, including mental disorders. Human beings possess between 80,000 and 100,000 genes, which contribute to every characteristic, including mental health. These genes interact with environmental factors to influence the development and progression of mental disorders [2]. While the presence of specific genes does not guarantee the onset of mental illness, certain genetic patterns have been associated with increased risk. For example, studies have shown a significant genetic component in disorders like schizophrenia and bipolar disorder, with heritability estimates of 64% and 59%, respectively [2,5].

It is well-established that mental health disorders result from a complex interplay between genetic predispositions and environmental factors. While genetic makeup can predispose individuals to certain conditions, environmental influences such as stress, trauma, and lifestyle choices can trigger or exacerbate these conditions [2,3,6]. This understanding underscores the importance of considering both genetic and environmental factors in mental health research and interventions [2,7].

The exploration of genetic influences on mental health has evolved significantly over the past few decades. The advent of molecular genetic techniques has enabled researchers to identify genes associated with mental disorders and understand their biological mechanisms [2,8]. The NIMH has been at the forefront of this research, supporting studies that investigate genetic factors in mental illness. Despite the complexity of genetic influences, progress in this field holds promise for developing targeted treatments and preventative strategies [2,9]. According to WHO statistics, one person dies by suicide every 40 seconds worldwide, amounting to 804,000 suicides each year. Nearly 80% of these cases are linked to mental health disorders, with depression being the most prevalent.

Main Content

Common mental health issues

Genetic factors are crucial in shaping the body's structure and function. Recent research has shown that abnormal variations in gene segments can lead to specific diseases. Modern medicine now utilizes gene mapping to diagnose conditions like sickle cell anemia, cystic fibrosis, and diabetes, which can adversely affect future generations. Majority of surveyed people (92%) confirmed that they don't think they have any mental health problems and have no intention to do mental health checking (77.6%). Even those with normal checking, most responded that they are not under any abnormal mental health condition nor using medicines (82% of participants).

Figure 1: Do You Have Mental Health Issues?

Source: Authors' survey

Even though only 26% of respondents report that their relatives have some mental health issues, most common are Anxiety (55%), Depression (47%), Schizophrenia (11%), bipolar disorder (13%) and autism spectrum disorder (8%). Anxiety and depression often manifest as chronic feelings of worry, sadness, or hopelessness, impacting daily functioning and quality of life. Schizophrenia and bipolar disorder, though less common, are severe mental health conditions that can profoundly affect a person's perception of reality, mood stability, and behavior. Autism spectrum disorder, a neurodevelopmental condition, affects social interaction, communication, and behavior, varying widely in its presentation and severity. Mental health issues within families and relatives highlights the importance of understanding and addressing the genetic and environmental factors that contribute to each individual's development. Despite the relatively low percentage of respondents reporting mental health issues in their relatives, the impact of these conditions is far-reaching, affecting not only the individuals diagnosed but also their families, caregivers, and communities.

Figure 2: Common Mental Health Issues

Source: Authors' survey

Anxiety disorders

Anxiety is the most popular issue among mental health reported by surveyed correspondents. More than half of them have the symptom of this disease. Anxiety disorders are a group of mental health conditions characterized by excessive and persistent worry, fear, or anxiety that interferes with daily life. Unlike normal anxiety, which is a temporary response to stress, anxiety disorders involve intense, prolonged feelings of apprehension that can disrupt an individual's ability to function in various aspects of life, such as work, school, and relationships. Common types of anxiety disorders include generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), panic disorder, social anxiety disorder, and specific phobias [3,4].

Anxiety disorders are among the most prevalent mental health conditions globally, affecting individuals across all age groups. They often begin in childhood or adolescence and can persist into adulthood if left untreated. According to the [3,10], women are more likely than men to be diagnosed with an anxiety disorder, with the lifetime prevalence for women being approximately 60% higher than for men. Additionally, individuals with a family history of anxiety disorders, those with chronic medical conditions, and those who have experienced significant life stressors are at increased risk of developing these conditions.

The symptoms of anxiety disorders can vary depending on the specific type but generally include excessive worry, restlessness, fatigue, difficulty concentrating, irritability, muscle tension, and sleep disturbances. Physical symptoms are also common, such as increased heart rate, sweating, trembling, dizziness, and shortness of breath. In severe cases, anxiety can lead to panic attacks, which are sudden episodes of intense fear accompanied by physical symptoms that can mimic those of a heart attack. In social anxiety disorder, individuals may experience intense fear in social situations, leading to avoidance of such interactions, which can significantly impact their social and occupational functioning. Specific phobias involve an irrational fear of specific objects or situations, such as heights, flying, or animals, which can also lead to avoidance behaviors that interfere with daily life. Generalized anxiety disorder is characterized by persistent, excessive worry about various aspects of life, often without a clear cause, leading to chronic stress and impaired functioning [4,11].

According to the survey, majority of people have encountered stress and worries in their daily lives (91.5%). These feelings, though common, can vary significantly in frequency and intensity. While more than half of the respondents reported that they do not experience stress and worry frequently, these emotions still make occasional appearances in their lives. The occasional experience of stress, though less

frequent, can still have a noticeable impact on an individual's overall well-being, potentially affecting their mood, productivity, and interpersonal relationships. Infrequent stress can contribute to longer-term mental health concerns if not properly managed.

Figure 3: The Frequency of Stress and Worries Experience

Source: Authors' survey

The causes of anxiety disorders are multifactorial, involving a combination of genetic, biological, environmental, and psychological factors. Genetic predisposition plays a significant role, with research indicating that anxiety disorders can run in families. Twin studies have shown that individuals with a first-degree relative who has an anxiety disorder are more likely to develop the condition themselves, suggesting a heritable component.

Biologically, anxiety disorders have been linked to imbalances in neurotransmitters, such as serotonin, norepinephrine, and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), which play key roles in regulating mood and stress responses. Abnormalities in the brain's fear circuitry, particularly in areas such as the amygdala and prefrontal cortex, are also implicated in the development of anxiety disorders. These abnormalities can lead to heightened sensitivity to perceived threats and difficulties in regulating emotional responses [3,12].

Environmental factors, including chronic stress, trauma, and significant life changes, can trigger or exacerbate anxiety disorders. For instance, individuals who have experienced childhood abuse, neglect, or a traumatic event are at a higher risk of developing anxiety disorders later in life. Psychological factors, such as personality traits like perfectionism, a tendency toward negative thinking, or a history of mental health disorders, can also increase susceptibility to anxiety disorders [2,13].

Depression

Depression is also a common issue of mental health. Nearly half of correspondents agreed that they have witnessed their relatives experienced this problem. Depression clinically referred to as major depressive disorder (MDD), is more than just feeling sad or having a bad day; it is a pervasive and chronic mental health condition that impacts how individuals feel, think, and manage daily activities. Unlike temporary feelings of sadness or grief, depression is a serious disorder that often requires long-term treatment and management. It manifests in a persistent low mood, a profound sense of hopelessness, and a lack of interest or pleasure in activities that were once enjoyable. These symptoms can significantly disrupt one's ability to function at work, at school, or in personal relationships [14].

Depression does not discriminate by age, gender, or socioeconomic status, although certain groups are more susceptible. It is most commonly diagnosed in adults, particularly those between the ages of 18 and 45. However, depression is also prevalent in adolescents, who may struggle with it during critical developmental stages. In older adults, depression can often go undiagnosed, as its symptoms may be mistaken for normal signs of aging, such as fatigue or loss of appetite [15].

Statistically, women are more likely to experience depression than men, with some studies suggesting that women are twice as likely to develop the disorder. This disparity may be attributed to biological differences, such as hormonal fluctuations during menstrual cycles, pregnancy, postpartum, and menopause, as well as sociocultural factors like gender roles and expectations. Additionally, individuals with chronic medical conditions, such as diabetes, heart disease, or chronic pain, are at a higher risk of developing depression. The burden of managing a long-term illness can exacerbate feelings of helplessness and hopelessness, contributing to the onset of depressive symptoms [16].

The symptoms of depression are varied and complex, often affecting both the mind and body. Emotionally, individuals with depression may experience overwhelming sadness, a sense of worthlessness, or intense guilt. They may lose interest in activities they once enjoyed, including hobbies, socializing, and even basic daily tasks. Physically, depression can manifest as changes in appetite, weight gain or loss, insomnia or excessive sleeping, and chronic fatigue. Cognitive symptoms, such as difficulty concentrating, making decisions, or remembering information, are also common [17].

One of the most concerning aspects of depression is its potential to lead to suicidal thoughts or behaviors. Individuals suffering from severe depression may feel that life is not worth living, and without proper

intervention, they may act on these thoughts. The relationship between depression and suicide is complex, and not everyone with depression will experience suicidal ideation. However, it is a critical aspect of the disorder that requires immediate attention and intervention [18].

The causes of depression are multifaceted, involving an interplay of genetic, biological, environmental, and psychological factors. From a genetic standpoint, depression often runs in families, suggesting a hereditary component. Research has identified specific genes that may increase the likelihood of developing depression, though the presence of these genes alone is not enough to cause the disorder. It is the interaction between genetic predispositions and environmental triggers—such as trauma, chronic stress, or significant life changes—that often leads to the onset of depression [19].

Biologically, depression has been linked to imbalances in neurotransmitters—chemicals in the brain that regulate mood. Serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine are three key neurotransmitters that have been extensively studied in relation to depression. For example, low levels of serotonin are often associated with feelings of sadness and despair, while imbalances in dopamine can affect motivation and pleasure. These biological factors can be influenced by genetics as well as external factors like stress or substance abuse [20].

Environmental factors, such as exposure to prolonged stress, childhood trauma, or significant life transitions (e.g., divorce, job loss, or the death of a loved one), can also trigger depression. These experiences can alter brain chemistry and structure, making an individual more vulnerable to developing depression. Psychological factors, including personality traits like low self-esteem, perfectionism, or a tendency towards negative thinking, further contribute to the risk of depression. Individuals who are prone to these traits may be more susceptible to interpreting life events in a way that exacerbates depressive symptoms [21].

Schizophrenia

Schizophrenia is a severe mental disorder that disrupts thought processes, perceptions, emotional responsiveness, and social interactions, impairing the ability to distinguish reality. It typically begins in late adolescence to early adulthood, between ages 16 and 30, with men often showing symptoms earlier than women. About 1% of the global population is affected, with no major ethnic or socio-economic differences in prevalence, although urban dwellers may be at higher risk. Symptoms are categorized into:

- **Positive Symptoms:** Hallucinations (e.g., auditory), delusions, and disorganized thinking.

- **Negative Symptoms:** Reduced emotional expression, loss of interest in activities, and social withdrawal.
- **Cognitive Symptoms:** Impaired attention, memory, and executive function.

The exact cause is unknown but involves a complex mix of genetic, biological, and environmental factors, including neurotransmitter imbalances, brain abnormalities, stress, and drug use. Schizophrenia has a substantial genetic component. Research indicates that individuals with a family history of schizophrenia have a higher risk of developing the disorder. The lifetime risk of schizophrenia is about 10% if a first-degree relative has the condition, compared to approximately 1% in the general population [22]. Twin and adoption studies further support the hereditary influence, with higher concordance rates for schizophrenia observed in monozygotic (identical) twins compared to dizygotic (fraternal) twins. Specific genes, such as those involved in neurotransmitter systems and neurodevelopment, have been implicated in increasing susceptibility to schizophrenia [23].

Recent research highlighted in the article "Common Genetic Factors Found in 5 Mental Disorders" by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) underscores shared genetic factors across several mental disorders, including schizophrenia. An international research consortium conducted a genome-wide association study (GWAS) involving over 33,000 patients and 28,000 controls. This study identified significant genetic variations in genes related to calcium channel regulation in neurons, particularly *CACNA1C* and *CACNB2*, which are linked to critical brain functions such as emotion, thinking, attention, and memory. Variations in chromosomes 3 and 10 were also associated with these disorders. Although individual genetic variations contribute minimally to risk, their collective impact is substantial, highlighting the biological basis of schizophrenia and related mental disorders. These findings could improve diagnostic accuracy and treatment approaches for schizophrenia and other mental health conditions.

Bipolar disorder

Bipolar disorder is a mental health condition marked by extreme mood swings between emotional highs (mania or hypomania) and lows (depression), affecting sleep, energy, behavior, and cognitive clarity. It typically emerges between ages 15 and 25, with earlier onset linked to a more severe course. It can also appear in childhood or later in life. Affects about 1% of the global population equally across genders and ethnic groups. Men often experience more manic episodes, while women may have more depressive episodes. Symptoms include elevated mood, high energy, rapid speech, racing thoughts, impulsivity, and reduced need for sleep during manic or hypomanic phases.

Depressive phases involve persistent sadness, loss of interest, fatigue, changes in sleep and appetite, and suicidal thoughts. The causes are not fully understood but involve a mix of genetic, biological, and environmental factors, including neurotransmitter imbalances and brain structure abnormalities.

Bipolar disorder is strongly linked to genetic and hereditary factors, with research demonstrating a heritability estimate of over 80%, underscoring the significant role of genetics in its development (Murray et al., 2017). Family studies reveal that individuals with a family history of bipolar disorder have a markedly higher risk of developing the condition, with first-degree relatives of affected individuals having a risk of approximately 10-20% compared to the general population's 1% [24].

Recent large-scale genetic research further supports these findings. A comprehensive study by the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) analyzed data from ten U.S. sites and identified several key genetic regions associated with bipolar disorder. The study utilized a genome-wide association scan involving 391 markers, revealing significant associations with chromosomal regions 17q and 6q ($P < .05$) and suggestive associations with regions 2p, 3q, and 8q ($P < .10$) (NIMH, 2024). These regions are linked to genes involved in neurotransmission and brain function, highlighting their relevance to the disorder.

Additional research, such as the large-scale GWAS meta-analysis by the Psychiatric Genomics Consortium, has identified several risk loci associated with bipolar disorder, including genes related to calcium channel regulation, such as *CACNA1C* and *CACNB2* (Psychiatric Genomics Consortium, 2018). These findings reinforce the genetic basis of bipolar disorder and illustrate how multiple genes contribute to susceptibility, providing insights into the complex interplay between genetics and environmental factors in the development of the disorder.

Autism spectrum disorder

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a complex neurodevelopmental condition characterized by challenges in social interaction, communication, and repetitive behaviors. The term "spectrum" reflects the wide variation in the type and severity of symptoms that individuals with ASD can experience. Some individuals with ASD may have significant cognitive impairments and require substantial support in daily life, while others may have average or above-average intelligence and function relatively independently [2]. The core features of ASD typically manifest in early childhood, usually before the age of three, and can affect various aspects of an individual's development throughout their life.

ASD is most commonly diagnosed in early childhood, typically around the age of two or three, when social

and communication difficulties become more apparent. However, some individuals may not receive a diagnosis until later in childhood or even adulthood, particularly those with milder symptoms who may initially be misdiagnosed or overlooked. ASD is about four times more common in boys than in girls, though girls with ASD often exhibit different symptom patterns, which can contribute to underdiagnosis or delayed diagnosis [4].

The prevalence of ASD has been steadily increasing over the past few decades, with current estimates suggesting that approximately 1 in 44 children in the United States is diagnosed with the condition. This increase is thought to be due to a combination of factors, including improved awareness, better diagnostic criteria, and possibly an actual increase in the number of cases [3]. The symptoms of ASD vary widely among individuals but generally include challenges in social communication and interaction, along with restricted and repetitive patterns of behavior. Social communication difficulties may manifest as a lack of eye contact, difficulty understanding social cues, delayed speech development, or unusual speech patterns, such as echolalia (repeating words or phrases). Individuals with ASD may also have difficulty forming and maintaining relationships, understanding the perspectives of others, or engaging in typical back-and-forth conversations [25].

Repetitive behaviors and restricted interests are another hallmark of ASD. These can include repetitive movements (e.g., hand-flapping, rocking), strict adherence to routines, and intense focus on specific topics or objects. Sensory sensitivities are also common, with individuals experiencing either hypersensitivity or hyposensitivity to stimuli such as light, sound, texture, or temperature. Some individuals with ASD may also have co-occurring conditions, such as anxiety, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), or intellectual disabilities, which can further complicate diagnosis and treatment [2].

The exact cause of ASD is not fully understood, but it is believed to be the result of a complex interplay of genetic and environmental factors. Genetics plays a significant role in the development of ASD, with studies showing that the condition tends to run in families. Specific gene mutations and chromosomal abnormalities have been linked to an increased risk of ASD, although no single genetic cause has been identified. Research indicates that hundreds of genes may contribute to the risk of developing ASD, each playing a small role in the overall genetic landscape of the disorder [26].

Environmental factors are also thought to contribute to the development of ASD. These can include prenatal factors such as advanced parental age, exposure to

certain medications during pregnancy, or complications during birth. Additionally, some studies have suggested that exposure to environmental toxins or infections during pregnancy may increase the risk of ASD, although more research is needed to confirm these findings. It is important to note that vaccines have been thoroughly studied and are not linked to the development of ASD, despite persistent myths and misinformation [6,27].

As the results, mental health has a close relationship with genetic factors. Majority of surveyed participants believed that genes play an important role in deciding mental health.

Figure 4: Do You Think Genes Affect to Mental Health?

Source: Authors' survey

This widespread belief in the importance of genetics in mental health underscores the need for increased genetic research and the development of personalized treatment approaches. This will lead to more accurate diagnoses, targeted therapies, and potentially even preventive measures for those at higher risk. It also highlights the importance of early intervention and the need for a holistic approach to mental health care that considers both genetic and environmental factors.

Solutions to Early Prevention and Treatment

Changing lifestyle and environmental condition

Lifestyle encompasses all aspects of human life, both spiritual and material, including thoughts, emotions, diet, work, study, rest, physical activity, sports, entertainment, and culture. Adopting a healthy and civilized lifestyle significantly benefits overall well-being. As society progresses, with improvements in material and spiritual life and advancements in healthcare, an individual's health increasingly depends on their own lifestyle choices.

The living and social environment encompasses factors such as beliefs, laws, culture, politics, economics, religion and social relationship. According to the survey's result, many people believe that both genes and environment affect to mental health development. These factors are interconnected and collectively shape

the living and social environment, influencing both individual and community health outcomes. Changing living environment can heavily influent on improving mental health issues.

Figure 5: Factors affecting Mental health
Source: Authors' survey

Combining various methods

Mental health treatment involves a variety of methods, each tailored to address different conditions and individual needs such as Pharmacotherapy, Psychotherapy, Electroconvulsive Therapy, Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation, Cognitive Remediation Therapy and so on.

Pharmacotherapy involves the use of medications to manage mental health disorders. These medications can help stabilize mood, reduce symptoms, and improve overall functioning. Psychotherapy, or "talk therapy," involves working with a trained therapist to explore thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. Electroconvulsive Therapy (ECT) involves applying brief electrical pulses to the brain under anesthesia to induce a controlled seizure. It is primarily used for severe depression, treatment-resistant depression, and other severe mental illnesses when other treatments have not been effective. Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) is a non-invasive procedure that uses magnetic fields to stimulate nerve cells in the brain. It is often used to treat depression, especially in patients who have not responded to other treatments. Cognitive remediation therapy focuses on improving cognitive functions such as memory, attention, and problem-solving skills. It is often used in treating schizophrenia, ADHD, and traumatic brain injury. Besides these methods, the doctors can combine with other social practice such as group therapy and family therapy, which are very useful in providing a supportive and positive environment.

Conclusion

Mental health is an important component of overall health, affecting how people think, feel, and behave in their daily lives. It includes a wide range of conditions, from common disorders such as anxiety and depression to more serious illnesses such as schizophrenia and bipolar disorder. Up to 91.5% of participants encountered stress and worries in their daily lives, which can further lead to anxiety and other mental health issues in the long term. Understanding the factors that contribute to mental health disorders is essential to developing effective prevention and treatment strategies. In the survey, 69.7% of correspondents agreed that both genes and environment can heavily affect to mental health. Genetics plays an important role in determining the risk of developing various mental health conditions. Just as genes influence physical traits such as eye color and height, they also influence brain function and behavior. Genetic research has revealed that many mental health disorders have a genetic component, meaning they can be passed down from one generation to the next. This genetic predisposition interacts with environmental factors to shape an individual's mental health outcomes. By examining the complex relationship between genetics and mental health, we can better appreciate the potential for improving mental health outcomes through genetic research and personalized care.

Methodology

- Surveys and Questionnaires: Develop a standardized survey that includes validated questions for measuring mental health as well as about participants' family history of mental illness, and their environmental factors (e.g., stress levels, living conditions).
- Data Collection Methods: Data collection methods were used to systematically gather information from participants, enabling the study to analyze the relationship between genetics and mental health. These methods ensured the accurate and reliable collection of data, providing a solid foundation for understanding the co-relationship.
- Data Analysis: Data analysis was used to systematically examine and interpret the collected data, allowing the study to identify issues and relationships between genetics and mental health in the community. Through statistical techniques and qualitative assessments, the analysis provided insights into how genetics affect mental health and lead to issues such as stress, anxiety, and depression.
- Information collection is used to systematically gather relevant data and insights from various sources or participants. This process is essential for understanding the scope of a research topic, ensuring that all necessary details are obtained to support analysis,

draw conclusions, and make informed decisions or recommendations based on the gathered information.

References

- [1] World Health Organization (Ed.). International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems: Alphabetical Index. Vol. 3. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2004.
- [2] National Institute of Mental Health. Looking at my genes: What can they tell me about my mental health? NIH Publications.
- [3] National Institute of Mental Health. Gene readouts contribute to distinctness of mental disorders. NIH News. 2022. <https://www.nimh.nih.gov/news/science-news/2022/gene-readouts-contribute-to-distinctness-of-mental-disorders.shtml>.
- [4] National Institutes of Health. Common genetic factors found in 5 mental disorders. NIH Research Matters. 2013. <https://www.nih.gov/news-events/nih-research-matters/common-genetic-factors-found-5-mental-disorders>.
- [5] Bloom B, Cohen RA, Freeman G. Summary health statistics for US children: National health interview survey, 2010. BMC Medicine. 2023; doi: 10.1186/s12916-020-01668-w.
- [6] BMC Medicine. Systems all the way down: Embracing complexity in mental health research. BMC Medicine. 2023. Doi: 10.1186/s12916-020-01668-w.
- [7] Dick DM, Foroud T. Genome wide linkage analysis of bipolar disorder: A new sample of 250 pedigrees from the NIMH genetics initiative. American Journal of Human Genetics. 2003. [https://www.cell.com/ajhg/fulltext/S0002-9297\(07\)63648-9](https://www.cell.com/ajhg/fulltext/S0002-9297(07)63648-9).
- [8] Stoewen DL. Nature, nurture, and mental health Part 1: The influence of genetics, psychology, and biology. The Canadian Veterinary Journal. 2022. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8922370/>.
- [9] Diagnostic, AP. Statistical manual of mental disorders. American Psychiatric Association. Washington, DC; 1987.
- [10] Dogra N, Singh SP, Svirydenka N, Vostanis P. Mental health problems in children and young people from minority ethnic groups: The need for targeted research. The British Journal of Psychiatry. 2012;200(4):265-267. Doi: 10.1192/bjp.bp.110.083469.
- [11] Duncan LE, et al. Largest GWAS of PTSD (N=20,070) yields genetic overlap with schizophrenia and sex differences in heritability. Molecular Psychiatry. 2017 Apr 25.
- [12] Hathaway B. Roots of major depression revealed in all their genetic complexity. YaleNews. 2021 May 27. <https://news.yale.edu/2021/05/27/roots-major-depression-revealed-all-their-genetic-complexity>.
- [13] Ivanova MY, Achenbach TM, Rescorla LA, et al. The generalizability of the Youth Self-Report syndrome structure in 23 societies. Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology. 2007;75(5):729. Doi: 10.1037/0022-006X.75.5.729.
- [14] JAMA Network. Genetic and environmental risk factors associated with trajectories of depression symptoms during adolescence and young adulthood. JAMA Psychiatry. 2023. doi: 10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2022.36940.
- [15] McCammon JM, Sive H. Addressing the genetics of human mental health disorders in model organisms. Annual Review of Genomics and Human Genetics. 2015. doi: 10.1146/annurev-genom-090314-050048.
- [16] Merikangas KR, Merikangas AK. Harnessing progress in psychiatric genetics to advance population mental health. American Journal of Public Health. 2019. doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2019.304948.
- [17] Kendler KS, Ohlsson H, Sundquist K, Sundquist J. Childhood adoption and mental health in adulthood: The role of gene-environment correlations. Behavior Genetics. 2023;53(1):1-10. doi: 10.1016/j.biopsych.2019.10.016.
- [18] Lambert MC, Lyubansky M, Achenbach TM. Behavioral and emotional problems among adolescents of Jamaica and the United States. Journal of Emotional and Behavioral Disorders. 1998;6(3):180-187. doi: 10.1177/106342669800600304.
- [19] Vendlinski MK, Javaras KN. Relative influence of genetics and shared environment on child mental health symptoms depends on comorbidity. Plos One. 2014. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0103080.
- [20] Mohammadi MR, Taylor E, Fombonne E. Prevalence of psychological problems amongst Iranian immigrant children and adolescents in UK. Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry. 2006.
- [21] Ohi K, Shimada T, Kataoka Y, Yasuyama T, Kawasaki Y, Shioiri T, Thompson PM. Genetic correlations between subcortical brain volumes and psychiatric disorders. The British Journal of Psychiatry. 2020;216(5):280-283. doi: 10.1192/bjp.2020.79.
- [22] Pettersson E, Lichtenstein P, Larsson H, Song J, Deficit A, Agrawal A, et al. Genetic influences on eight psychiatric disorders based on family data of 4,408,646 full and half-siblings, and genetic data of 333,748 cases and controls. Psychol Med. 2019;49(7):1166-1173. doi: 10.1017/S0033291718002039.
- [23] Hyman SE. The genetics of mental illness: Implications for practice. Bull World Health Organ. 2000;78(4):455-463. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2560734/>.

[24] Sajatovic M, Ramirez LF. Rating Scales in Mental Health. Baltimore, MD: JHU Press; 2012.

[25] Sanchez K, Chapa T, Ybarra R, Martinez ON. Eliminating disparities through the integration of behavioral health and primary care services for racial and ethnic minority populations, including individuals with limited English proficiency: A literature review report. United States Department of Health and Human Services, Office of Minority Health; 2012.

[26] Szekely E, Pappa I, Wilson JD, Bhamidi S, Jaddoe VW, Verhulst FC, et al. Childhood peer network characteristics: Genetic influences and links with early mental health trajectories. *J Child Psychol Psychiatry*. 2016;57(6):687-694. doi: 10.1111/jcpp.12516.

[27] Yang H, Chen X, Chen ZB, Li L, Li XY, Castellanos FX, et al. Disrupted intrinsic functional brain topology in patients with major depressive disorder. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2021;26(12):7363-7371. doi: 10.1038/s41380-021-01070-6.